

1 **STK kinase fingerprint is a record of Xist control of cellular identity.**

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7 Nuclear factors including TCF factors and TLE co-repressors control cellular identity but cytoplasmic
8 effectors that reflect unique cellular identities also exist. STK kinases represent a large family of enzymes
9 whose selective activation and repression patterns we propose reflect a record of selection pressure and
10 cellular evolution and are a component of cellular identity. The non-coding RNA Xist has known functions
11 pertinent to clonal selection. We measured total transcription in human cells with artificially engineered
12 integration of Xist at unique genomic sites and observed prominent STK kinase activation and repression
13 suggesting direct control of the STK gene family expression by Xist: Xist could control the expression of
14 STK36, STK4 and STK24 expression in a specific and quantitatively significant manner. Accordingly, when
15 measuring total transcription in human embryonic stem cells and comparing the hES transcriptome
16 between males or females, which feature Xist as among the largest transcriptional differences, STK36,
17 STK4 and STK24 were among the genes expressed most significantly different in the human ES cell
18 transcriptome based on sex. The STK kinase fingerprint of each cell and tissue type is a developmental
19 record that leaves an imprint that is likely a component of cellular identity, with an evident contribution of
20 Xist to cellular evolution and clonal selection through sex-specific control of a unique STK kinase
21 repertoire by Xist.
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